

The Price of a Bride : Dowry in Modern India and The Gaps in Legal Reform

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Abstract

Despite being prohibited and reformed for decades, dowry remains a deep-rooted socio-cultural practice in India. This research analyses the nature of dowry where it persists in modern Indian society and the limitations of existing and newly codified legal frameworks. Major provisions relating to dowry had been retained, with a minor change, by the Indian Penal Code (IPC), 1860 that had been replaced by the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS) in 2023. Nevertheless, the BNS does not contemplate how to deal with the structural and systemic deficiencies that allow dowry practices to thrive in the name of gifts or social customs. This research analyzes the cultural, economic, legal aspects of dowry; compares urban from rural pattern and other enforcement gaps, societal apathy and misuse theories that weaken the law. The research argues that legal reform alone is not enough without combined work in socio education and change at the community level. The research proposes suggestions for a holistic reform, which includes legislative clarity, stronger enforcement, gender sensitization as well as economic empowerment that will bridge the gap between law and lived reality of Indian women.

Keywords

Dowry Death, Domestic Violence, Gender Justice, Women's Rights, Patriarchy, Social Norms

Introduction

India's persistent dowry crisis was again in a chilling reminder, with the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) reporting 6,450 dowry related deaths in 2022 itself, an average of nearly 17 women being killed every day as a result of dowry harassment [1]. Public outrage over such cases as that of the brutal death of woman, Vismaya Nair in Kerala (found dead in her marital home after sustaining long hours of dowry related trauma) highlight the systemic gaps in societal accountability as well as legal deterrence [2]. Despite the making of major legal reforms as well as criminalization of dowry practices, the culture of making brides a commodity remains strong and remains a part of the social milieu disguised under the gloss of 'customary gifts' and 'marriage expenses'.

While the dowry system in India has become largely coercive, there is a long tradition of stridhan, where wealth and assets were given to women voluntarily as a way of financial security at the time of marriage. But over centuries or since colonial era, this system became of transactional and extractive nature, which is sanctioned by patriarchal values and further reinforced by caste and class hierarchies.

Objective of study

Dowry is now a social obligation that places tremendous financial responsibilities on the families of brides, while legitimizing a spectrum of gender-based violence that includes physical and mental harassment, abuse and even death. While the formal criminalization of dowry under the Dowry Prohibition Act, (DPA) 1961 and related penal provisions, the practice continues to be rampant in rural as well as urban settings across socioeconomic strata [3].

Review of Literature

Dowry Prohibition Act, (DPA) 1961 and related penal provisions, the practice continues to be rampant in rural as well as urban settings across socioeconomic strata. Dowry related offences were, for over a century and a half, the province of IPC, 1860, particularly Section 304B (dowry death) and Section 498A (cruelty by husband or relatives). These provisions have been reorganized but substantially retained under Section 80 and 85 respectively with the enactment of the BNS, 2023, which is to replace the IPC from July 1, 2024. The legislative shift is a symbolic break from colonial jurisprudence but the replication of IPC era provisions in the BNS without any doctrinal or structural reform raises doubts about whether the new code will be able to effect any change in bringing an end to the dowry crisis. The lack of proactive and preventive mechanisms means that punitive frameworks continue, and that there are no real legal mechanisms to change, in what is, in the end, the absence of proactive and preventive mechanisms to combat a deeply cultural and socio-economic malaise [4].

Main Text

The Evolution of Dowry in India

The institution of dowry in India in its earliest connotation was not in itself oppressive, but was stridhan, a kind of movable property voluntarily given to the bride by her natal family as a guarantee of security and independence. According to Manusmriti and

Smritis, stridhan was the woman's exclusive property which was not under the legal control of her husband and his kin. While this relatively equitable construct only began to span under colonialism, it underwent a stunning distortion in that interval. British legal code and their misapprehension of indigenous practice codified dowry as an obligatory payment to the bride's family and its parochial understandings of dowry's maternal protective purpose as formal law. Dowry, like cash dowry, became normalized in the colonial matrimonial context due to upper castes' indirect reliance on upper caste Brahminical customs and thus embedded coercive economic structure within the matrimonial frame [5].

Largely, and for many reasons, socioeconomic stratification was firmly rooted on the axes of caste, class and gender, and it only augmented this historical deviation from stridhan to exploitative dowry. Dowry in such a rigidly hierarchical society functioned as a symbol of status and, at the same time, as a means of social mobility for those castes and classes within an upwardly aspirational social order that wished to emulate elite marriage practices. The commodification of brides indexed brides' 'value' in terms of beauty, fertility, education and most importantly, the dowry that they brought with them reflected and entrenched gendered inequities. Dowry was a proxy for male economic and social capital in the marriage market and women were reduced to liabilities unless accompanied by a large material counter compensation. Dowry has been sustained as a structural tool of gender oppression through the nexus of cultural normativity and economic expectation, which have been so deeply embedded socio religious and economic incentives, so that legal prohibitions have been insufficient to the task [6].

Legal Framework Governing Dowry in India

The DPA, 1961, IPC, 1860 (now BNS, 2023) and Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005 (PWDVA) form the legal framework for dowry in India. The DPA, 1961 expressly criminalizes the giving, taking, or demanding of dowry prior to, during or after marriage, and defines dowry in a wide sense to include any property or valuable security given in connection with marriage. BNS, 2023 (IPC, 1860) criminalizes the cruelty by a husband or relatives of the husband especially where such cruelty is connected with dowry harassment and is punishable with imprisonment for a term which may extend to three years. These are complemented by the purview of civil remedies in case of domestic violence, including acts of dowry coercion and economic abuse, that can be met out through protection orders, residence orders and maintenance relief under the purview of PWDVA to broaden the ambit of legal recourse from the confines of criminal prosecution.

These laws, however, despite their individual and collective intent to curb dowry related abuse, are notable strong. The normative framework of the DPA's categorical prohibition on dowry is designed to deter the practice in all strata. Section 498A is a strong deterrent to systemic abuse of the marital home by treating psychological and physical harassment as punishable crimes. The PWDVA is civil in nature and a more flexible, victim centric mechanism that allows women to get immediate relief without the rigors of criminal litigation. They have a multi-tiered approach, prohibition (DPA), penal sanctions (IPC/BNS) and civil safeguards (PWDVA). The tripartite legal structure hypothesizes to address dowry violence by addressing the multifaceted nature of dowry violence, economic coercion, emotional trauma and physical abuse [7].

However, as this otherwise comprehensive legal framework is, enforcement is the Achilles heel. The ingrained patriarchal attitudes, lack of training, procedural lapses and often lack of response on the part of investigative agencies to complaints are often uncaring and insensitive, despite the complaints being reported by women. Further eroded is the deterrent effect of the criminal provisions by judicial delays and low conviction rates, and when women attempt to use these laws, their case is frequently subjected to societal pressures to reconcile rather than litigate. These NGOs and legal aid cells have been instrumental in plugging the gap between law and access to justice, but part of the reason they are unable to go beyond a certain distance is resource constrained and lack of consistent institutional support. Additionally, a regressive discourse has emerged around concerns regarding misuse that favors the accused's rights at the expense of lived realities of victims, lending a climate of enforcement. The existing legal regime without reforms to strengthen investigative capacity, sensitize judicial actors and widen preventative outreach will not be a substantial one that can eradicate dowry violence [8].

Judicial Perspectives

The DPA, 1961 was a significant legislative measure aimed at curbing the widespread social evil of dowry. However, its initial language was vague and narrow, limiting its effectiveness. Section 2 originally used the phrase "as consideration for the marriage," which the courts interpreted restrictively, as in *Inder Sain v. State*, [9]. where it was ruled that dowry referred only to property exchanged as compensation or reward for marriage, and not to demands made after the marriage. Recognizing this limitation, the Act was amended to replace this with broader terms such as "in connection with the marriage" and included property exchanged "any time after the marriage," to close loopholes and expand legal protection.

The judgment in *Sanjay Kumar Jain v. State of Delhi* [10] emphasized the moral and social urgency to address dowry-related issues, labeling dowry deaths as a "slur and curse" on Indian society. The case reiterated the importance of strict enforcement and

societal reform. It also highlighted the legal mechanism under Section 6 of the DPA, 1961, which mandates the return of dowry articles to the bride within three months, failing which it becomes a punishable offence. Further, the Supreme Court in *Pratibha Rani v. Suraj Kumar* [11] classified the wrongful retention of these articles as criminal breach of trust under Section 405 of the Indian Penal Code, reinforcing the idea that dowry-related offences are both social and criminal wrongs.

The Joint Parliamentary Committee review, 1982 revealed the act's inefficacy due to two main reasons: a flawed definition of dowry and a weak enforcement structure. However, post-1982 amendments attempted to address these concerns by refining the definition and strengthening the enforcement framework. A landmark ruling in *Satbir Singh v. State of Haryana* [12] reaffirmed this progress by stating that once the prosecution proves essential ingredients under Section 304-B IPC (dowry death), the burden shifts to the accused to prove innocence. This reversal of burden marked a stringent and more effective approach toward punishing dowry-related crimes.

The interpretation of the phrase "soon before death" in dowry death cases has been a point of contention. In *Mustafa Shahadal Shaikh v. State of Maharashtra*, [13] the court clarified that the law does not specify a fixed time frame for this term. Instead, courts are to assess each case based on its specific facts and circumstances. The rationale is that the cruelty or harassment leading to death must be proximate in time and psychologically linked to the woman's condition before her demise. If the mistreatment occurred too long before the death, it loses legal relevance, thus emphasizing the necessity for timely and connected evidence.

Gaps and Challenges in Legal Reforms

Due to a chronic and well documented implementation deficit, anti-dowry laws in India are routinely illusory in practice. Although DPA, 1961 & penal provisions under BNS, 2023 exist, systemic under reporting of the cases renders the efficacy of these laws ineffective. The primary reason victims avoid reporting complaints is because of fear of retaliation, social ostracization, economic dependency, and, of course, the threat of social and familial pressure. Even more silence is brought upon potential complainants by the stigma associated with the shame they would bring upon one's marital home or natal family. The result of such underreporting is not only statistical understatement but a broken justice system failing to record and respond to the ways that dowry related abuse is lived. This is compounded by the fact that dowry death and cruelty are not convicted often, which reflects evidentiary obstacles, witness reluctance as well as procedural lapses preventing prosecution, leading to impunity [14]

Further, polarized discourse on the purported misuse of Section 498A of IPC which criminalizes cruelty by the husband or his kin is the critical issue. Despite being brought in as a progressive step to empower women who are subjected to domestic violence as well as dowry harassment, this provision has been repeatedly subjected to judicial and political scrutiny for misuse. The Supreme Court in *Rajesh Sharma v. State of U.P.* reiterated for a need to have safeguards against false accusations, but excessive narrative of misuse has had the crushing effect on public and legal perception respectively but for real victims. The law has been framed in such an artificial binary of misuse versus underuse that actually the complaint of misuse is met with skepticism, and chills reporting and reduces the deterrent value of the law. In so balancing the law of due process and protection, the legal system has not been able to establish a framework that does not over criminalize or otherwise make the law ineffectual.

Perhaps the absolutely insidious barrier to reform are sociocultural factors. The dowry system, although legally prohibited, is legitimized culturally as tradition, honor or customary gifting. The continued normalization of dowry in fact, perpetuates gender hierarchies and commodifies women as part of the marital transaction with the tacit support of the community. Subtle coercion makes women conform to dowry norms, and those who refuse will be socially excluded or may face marital instability. Such an environment condemns legal reform alone; because in such an environment, laws that fail to dig into the socio-normative basis of gender inequality will not act. Historically, the judiciary and legislature have treated dowry as a separate criminal problem rather than a manifestation of the broader problem of societal misogyny, opting to separate the law from the rest of the cultural transformation [15]

Implementation of dowry laws is hampered by the lack of legal literacy which is widespread. The majority of the population, especially in rural and semi-urban areas, is unaware of their rights under the DPA, 1961 or under BNS, 2023. The system has excluded it, not an accident, but a product of systemic exclusion from legal and educational institutions. It has often been the case that women do not have access to legal counsel, support networks or even the basic knowledge to travel the criminal justice system. The state has not invested enough in community level awareness programs or institutional mechanisms which could enable women to become empowered before, during or after a marriage or a dispute or an act of violence. Fulfilling the extremely often aspirational instead of actionable reforms requires proactive advocacy, procurement of legal awareness and grassroots mobilization. As a result, it requires us to radically change both policy priorities and implement strategies to bridge the gap between formal legal framework and the process of materialization [16].

Conclusion

However, this does not indicate that punitive legal model can address a deeply entrenched socio-cultural malaise as the persistence of dowry related violence and coercion in India continues, even in the existence of a robust formal legal architectural under DPA, 1961 & BNS. The failure of the BNS to make substantive legal innovation and preventive frameworks shows that the BNS did not take full advantage of this opportunity for transformative reform. The mere reproduction of existing legal doctrines without the reforms in the procedural fields, the accountability mechanism in the institutions, or socio-legal engagement mechanism addresses to a dynamic and break pace challenge in the social sphere through the static legal response. Now, the move is towards a multidimensional approach that would boost enforcement infrastructure, replete restorative and rehabilitative justice for survivors, and densely sensitized community-based programs. The legislative reform shall also be very clear with definitional definition of dowry from voluntary gifts to ensure that there is no misuse but that it is calibrated with shield of misuse and also mandate that there be premarital financial disclosures so that the transaction is transparent. Law thus has to pre-empt, to educate and to empower and, in doing so, it has to reshape social attitudes as much as statutory norms.

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